

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

PRIMARY CARE SURGERY IN FAMILY MEDICINE DEPARTMENT LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL (LASUTH): A 7-YEAR REVIEW OF DAY CASE SURGERIES AND OUTCOMES

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Abstract

Background: The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified the training of Family Physicians (FPs) as critical to meeting the primary care surgery needs of the underserved populations. Many countries including high income ones have reported increased health coverage for patients when FPs are equipped and allowed to perform procedures for common and life-saving medical conditions.

Objective: To review the surgeries performed by the Family Medicine department LASUTH and their outcome over a period of seven years and compare the outcomes with the standard.

Methodology: It was a retrospective review of records of patients who had surgeries and other procedures from 2015 to October 2022. A total of 1001 surgeries and procedures were carried out, however only 953 had the required information for analysis. Analysis was done using SPSS version 25.

Result: Majority of the patients (46.5%) were between the ages of 20-39 years. Over half (56.2%) of the patients were females. Excision biopsy for breast lump was the most common surgery (42.6 %) followed by Herniorrhaphy (29.5%) and Lipoma excision (12.3%). Majority of the histology reports were benign lesions, however there were six masses excised.

Conclusion: The findings from this review reinforces the critical role of family physicians in providing surgical care especially in this era of shortage of surgeons in Nigeria and worldwide. Primary surgery is an essential part of Family Medicine curriculum and its practice should be encouraged to get best outcomes as part of multidisciplinary care.

Keywords: Family Physicians, Primary care surgery, Benign lesions, Excision biopsy, Herniorrhaphy

Introduction

Primary Care is the provision of integrated, accessible health care services by Clinicians who are accountable for addressing a large majority of personal health care needs, developing a sustained partnership with patients, and practicing in the context of family and community.¹ A primary health care view point is vital for addressing the unmet need for essential surgical care in rural communities in low- and middle-income countries.² Within the framework of primary

health care, surgery could become part of an integrated approach to health-care delivery that is informed by local needs and priorities and that actively engages community stakeholders and community development organizations involved in public health.² Family medicine is a branch of medicine that manages common and long-term illnesses in children and adults, by providing comprehensive, continuing and holistic care.^{3,4} The World Health Organization has identified the training of family physicians as critical to meeting

the primary care surgery needs of the underserved populations.⁵ Thus, Family Physicians are the perfect candidates for providing surgical care within the framework of primary care once they have undergone training in the surgical, obstetric and anesthesia skills required.⁶ Many countries including high income ones have reported increased health coverage for patients when family physicians are equipped and allowed to perform procedures for common and life-saving medical conditions.⁶

Minor surgical procedures are defined as a set of procedures in which short surgical techniques are applied on superficial tissues, usually with local anesthesia, and minimal complications, that usually do not require postoperative resuscitation and need minimal equipment, many of which are used on a daily basis, and can be easily and safely performed in a short amount of time.^{7,8,9}

In high-income countries, it is well established that training family physicians in additional surgical, obstetric or anesthesia skills after their generalist training is very effective and is essential for those working in remote areas where it is daunting, expensive or risky to transfer patients to a central facility for routine procedures.¹⁰ The curriculum of Family Physicians in different countries such as the West African college, the National post graduate college of Nigeria as well as the curriculum in Canada, Australia and the United States of America, have provided a guide on the scope of surgical practices that Family Physicians should be skilled in which include surgical procedures such as Appendectomy, Hernia repair, Caesarian section, Orthopaedic fractures amongst others.^{10,11,12} A lot of minor surgical procedures constitute day case surgeries which are gaining popularity worldwide in a bid to reduce waiting times, use of bed space and promote patient satisfaction.¹² In Kenya and Nepal, where most citizens live in far reaching rural areas, most surgical specialists are located in large urban referral hospitals, leaving emergency surgical care in district and county hospitals to be dealt with by General Physicians.⁶ Their Ministries of Health has designated Family Physicians as “the most appropriate personnel to respond to the challenges of the health service delivery system” because of their ability to provide “continuous, comprehensive and cost-effective health care to individuals, families and

communities.”⁶ For example, over a period of 4 years, Kabarak University trained Family Medicine residents to independently diagnose and manage common, urgent and emergent problems that may require surgery, including Paediatric, Obstetric and Gynecological, Orthopedic and General surgery. The training enabled Family Physicians to become competent in managing common emergencies in these sub-specialities.⁶

It is therefore important to introduce and popularize the concept of day case surgery, as this may help hospitals and healthcare providers to streamline resources by reducing length of hospital stay, decreasing morbidity and mortality, and providing valuable bed services to emergencies.¹³

It also helps to reduce time lost away from work and indirectly helps to decrease loss of revenue for the individual and state. Many hospitals in Nigeria provide day care services with patients admitted to the general surgical wards, and no dedicated day surgery units (DSUs), as currently practiced in developed countries.¹³

Methods

Study setting

The study was conducted in the family medicine department of Lagos State University Teaching Hospital Ikeja (LASUTH), Lagos, Nigeria. Lagos State is located in South Western,

Nigeria with a total of 20 local government areas and 37 local council development areas. Lagos was the former capital of Nigeria, a cosmopolitan state and is the commercial nerve center of the nation. It has an estimated population of 24.6million.¹⁸⁴

Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH) is situated within the central business area of Ikeja Local Government of the State. It is located at 1-5 Oba Akinjobi way, Ikeja. It serves as a training, research, and referral center offering primary, secondary and tertiary care services. The hospital currently has a complement of consultants in various specialties including Family Medicine.

The Family Medicine Department of LASUTH, runs different areas of special interest clinics/units which includes: The Chronic Medical Disorder (CMD) Clinic, National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) Clinic, Geriatric Clinic, Lifestyle Medicine clinic, Retroviral disease (HIV) clinic,

the General Outpatient Clinic (GOPC) and the primary care surgery unit. These clinics serve as primary care clinics within a tertiary hospital setting and are manned by consultant family physicians, resident doctors and various cadres of medical officers. The primary surgery unit is run in collaboration with the primary health center, Abule Onigbagbo, where the surgeries are carried out. The Primary health center has 2 theatres and 5 beds which are used for same day admissions and recovery postoperatively before discharge. Patients with surgical pathologies which can be managed as day case surgeries using local anesthesia and occasionally total intravenous anesthesia are recruited for surgery at the PHC.

Study design

The study was a retrospective review of records of patients who had surgeries and other procedures from 2015 to October 2022. The files with required information such as bio-data, diagnosis, surgery done, histology reports among others were analyzed.

Data Collection

All patients sign consent forms prior to surgical procedures, and the information obtained was collected without patient identifiers. Case files which could not be retrieved were excluded. A total of 1001 surgeries and procedures were done, however only 953 (95.2%) had required information. A total 581 patients had histology done on their samples, however only 257(44.23%) of the results could be retrieved from the files. Phone calls were made to patients who had herniorrhaphy, in addition to files being assessed for information on long-term complications.; 167 (59.4%) were contacted. The age, gender, type of surgery done, details of histology report were collected and phone calls were made to patients who had herniorrhaphy to ask questions about long-term complications such as reoccurrence, chronic pain, amongst others.

Analysis

Results were analysed using the SPSS 22 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences [SPSS] Inc., Rochester, MN, US). Statistics were presented in tabular and descriptive forms.

Ethical consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical committee of LASUTH, Ikeja (Registration number NHREC04/04/2008, Reference number

LREC.06/10/793. Confidentiality was maintained as data were anonymized.

Results

A total of 953 surgeries were carried out, with the largest number in 2019 with 158 surgeries and only 66 surgeries done in 2020 as shown in Figure 1. Almost half 444(46.59%) of the patients were between the ages of 20-39 years, while elderly patients (older 60 years of age) made up 114(11.96%) of the patients (Figure 2). A majority, 536(56.2%) of the patients were females as shown in Figure 3.

Breast Lumpectomy, 406 (42.6%), was the most common surgery performed with Herniorrhaphy 281(29.5%) and Lipoma excisions (12.1%) other commonly performed procedures. Ganglion excision, 11(1.0%) was the least performed surgery as shown in Table 1

Fibroadenoma was the most common breast lump lesion excised as shown in figure 4, with Lipoma the most common non breast masses (table 2). There were six malignant masses as shown in table 3. Less than 10% of the patients had long term complications from inguinal herniorrhaphy as shown in table 4.

Discussion

Breast lump excision was the most commonly performed surgery (41.6%) as reported in another study and there were no serious complications reported.¹⁵ There has been a continuous effort to improve the investigation of breast masses, while ensuring aesthetic procedures especially as majority of benign breast lumps occur in younger women. The few cases of malignant histology occurred despite pre-evaluation with fine needle biopsies, clinical evaluation and scans; this highlights the importance of Trucut biopsies prior to surgery in high risk patients (e.g. those with family history of cancers, suspicious ultrasound, FNAC –C3-C5, age >35 years among others).¹⁶ Inguinal hernias are one of the most common surgical procedures and accounted for about one third of the surgeries carried out in this review. Inguinal hernia repair has a recurrence rate of 0.5%–10.0%, following primary repair. Other complications include chronic pain (0.7%–62.9 %), wound infection (1.0%–7.0%), urinary retention (0.2%–22.2%), hypoesthesia (4.3%–67.0%).¹⁷

Table 1: Distribution of Procedures

Type of Surgery	Frequency(N-953)	Percentage (%)
Breast Lump Excision	406	42.6
Herniorrhaphy	281	29.5
Lipoma Excision	117	12.3
Excision of Masses	47	4.9
Ingrowing toe nail	43	4.5
Hydrocelectomy	25	2.6
Incision and Drainage	13	1.4
Pyogenic Granuloma	11	1.2
Ganglion	10	1.0

Table 2: Histology of non-breast masses

Histology	Frequency (N-66)	Percentage (%)
Lipoma	37	56
Fibrolipoma	8	12
Fibroepithelila polyp	4	6.5
Pyogenic granuloma	3	4.5
Sebaceous cyst	3	4.5
Cavernous haemangioma	2	3
Verruca Vulgaris	2	3
Tubular Adenoma	2	3
TB Adenitis	1	1.5
Squamous Papilloma	1	1.5
Molluscum Contagiosum	1	1.5
Osteochondroma	1	1.5
Trichoepithelioma	1	1.5

Table 3: Showing Malignant Histology

Site	Histology	Frequency (N-6)
Breast	Invasive Ductal carcinoma	3
Lymph node	Hodgkins Lymphoma (mixed cellularity)	2
	Metastatic Lymph node	1

Table 4 Showing Long Term Complications Following Herniorrhaphy

Complications	Frequency (N=167)	Percentage (%)
1.No	154	91.6
2. Yes	13	8.38
a) Recurrence	05	2.99
b) Chronic Pain	08	4.8

Figure 1: Number of procedures (n= 953)

Figure 2: Age group of patients N-953

Figure 3: Gender distribution of patients

Figure 4 : Histology of Breast Masses

The complications are determined by many factors including patient related (e.g. gender, age, comorbidities and the subjective perception of symptoms) and institutional factors (e.g. surgeon's experience, method of repair, type of anesthesia and duration of follow-up).¹⁷ A study in Singapore reported that hernia surgery complications were similar in general hospitals

and dedicated hernia centers as long as protocols and continuous teaching occurred.¹⁷ Similarly a prospective study in Ghana showed non inferior complication rates between hernia surgeries carried out at primary care and by surgeons.¹⁸ The reported prevalence of complications for hernia surgeries like recurrence and pain from our audit is low and within reported rates from world class

centers using open hernia repair technique.^{18,19,20} This is probably due to instituted protocols, good supervision and proper selection of cases of hernia performed at the PHC.

Conclusion

The findings from this review reinforces the critical role of family physicians in providing surgical care especially in this era of shortage of surgeons in Nigeria and worldwide. Primary surgery is an essential part of Family Medicine curriculum and its practice should be encouraged to get best outcomes as part of multidisciplinary care.

The primary care surgery programme in LASUTH which incorporates the primary health care is a model which can be adopted to improve the health indices in state especially for underserved populations. There is need for continuous up-skilling which should be in conjunction with the relevant surgical specialties. Regular auditing of procedures and outcomes is necessary to ensure best clinical outcomes for patients. There is potential to expand the programme and include more common therapeutic and diagnostic procedures.

Declarations

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Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

None

Ethics approval

The research was approved by Lagos State University Teaching Hospital Health Research and Ethics Committee (HREC).

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